

Synthesis and characterization of Mg^{II}, Ca^{II}, Sr^{II} and Ba^{II} complexes of 2,13-dimethyl-3,14-diethyl/propyl/phenyl-1,4,12,15-tetraazacyclodocosa-1,3,12,14-tetraene

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Abstract : Mg^{II}, Ca^{II}, Sr^{II} and Ba^{II} complexes of the general formula [MLX₂] (where L = tetraazamacrocycle having 22-membered ring and X = Cl⁻ or NCS⁻) have been synthesized by 2+2 cyclocondensation of 1,7-diaminoheptane with α-diketones viz. 2,3-pentanedione, 2,3-hexanedione or 1-phenyl-1,2-propanedione in the presence of metal ions as templates. The resulting macrocyclic complexes have been characterized by elemental analyses (M, N and Cl), conductances and IR and ¹H NMR spectral studies.

Keywords : Macrocyclic complexes, ¹H NMR spectra.

During the recent years interest has developed in the field of macrocyclic complexes due to their close resemblance with the naturally occurring biological systems and a variety of azamacrocycles have been synthesized. Generally transition metal ions have been used as templates in the condensation reactions of diamines with α- and β-diketones resulting in the formation of azamacrocyclic complexes¹. However, alkaline earth metal ions have also been used as templates. Ca^{II}, Sr^{II} and Ba^{II} complexes of 18- and 24-membered azamacrocycles derived from 2,6-diformyl- or 2,6-diacetylpyridine have been reported². In continuation of our earlier work on alkaline earth metal complexes of 18-membered tetraazamacrocycles derived from (2+2) cyclocondensation of α-diketones and 1,5-diaminopentane³, we report herein the synthesis of Mg^{II}, Ca^{II}, Sr^{II} and Ba^{II} complexes of 22-membered tetraazamacrocycles derived from 1,7-diaminoheptane and α-diketones such as 2,3-pentanedione, 2,3-hexanedione or 1-phenyl-1,2-propanedione.

Results and discussion

The reactions of metal chlorides or nitrates with 1,7-diaminoheptane and α-diketones such as 2,3-pentanedione, 2,3-hexanedione or 1-phenyl-1,2-propanedione in 1 : 2 : 2 molar ratios (in the presence of NCS⁻ ions in case of Ca, Sr and Ba) have afforded M^{II} complexes (1) of 22-membered tetraazamacrocycles 2,13-dimethyl-3,14-diethyl/propyl/phenyl-1,4,12,15-tetraazadocosa-1,3,12,14-tetraene according to general Scheme 1.

Scheme 1. Synthesis of alkaline earth metal complexes of tetraazamacrocycles.

10-Membered chelate rings in these complexes are not improbable due to their flexibility as such larger rings have been reported earlier in case of the complexes of long chain flexible bidentate ligands such as Co^{III} complexes of diaminoalkanes H₂N(CH₂)_nNH₂ (n = 2–14) and platinum and palladium complexes of diphosphines Bu^t₂P(CH₂)_nPBu^t₂ (n = 9, 10 or 12)^{4,5}. Moreover, such a chelate ring would be more stable in metal complexes of macrocyclic ligands since macrocyclic complexes are often stabilized to a greater extent by the macrocyclic effect 'multiple juxtapositional fixedness'⁶.

The resulting macrocyclic complexes were isolated as yellow or brown solids. They decompose on heating and are insoluble in chloroform, carbon tetrachloride and *n*-hexane but soluble in DMSO. The analyses and characteristics of the complexes are given in Table 1.

Molar conductances of the complexes are generally low (Table 1) supporting their non-electrolytic behaviour. Thus the chloro or thiocyanato groups appear to be coordinated. However, the higher values of conductances in some cases may be due to the replacement of weakly coordinated chloro or thiocyanato groups by solvent molecules.

Infrared spectra :

All the complexes exhibit a strong band at 1580–1640 cm^{-1} attributable to the coordinated $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ and no absorption band at 1700 or 3200–3300 cm^{-1} is observed due to unreacted $\text{C}=\text{O}$ or NH_2 groups. Similar observations have been made by other workers in case of metal complexes of other macrocycles⁷. A broad band at ~ 550 cm^{-1} is observed due to metal-nitrogen stretching vibrations. N-Bonded thiocyanate stretching frequencies are observed at 2050–2080 cm^{-1} . Lowering of this frequency as compared to that reported for free thiocyanate (2100 cm^{-1}) supports the coordination of thiocyanate to the metal atom⁸.

Nuclear magnetic resonance spectra : ^1H NMR spectra of Mg^{II} complexes have been recorded and the δ values (ppm) for different protons are given in Table 2. In free diamine the $\alpha\text{-CH}_2$ protons appear as a triplet at δ 2.68 ppm, while β and other CH_2 protons appear as a quintet at δ 1.35 ppm. In KIM (2) the $\alpha\text{-CH}_2$ protons have been reported to appear as a triplet at δ 3.64 ppm and $\beta\text{-CH}_2$ protons as a quintet at δ 2.11 ppm⁹. This downfield shift as compared to the protons of free diamines is due to deshielding by π -electrons of $\text{C}=\text{N}$ bond. The free macrocycles, though not isolated, would have exhibited these resonances at almost similar positions as in KIM. In the macrocyclic complexes of Mg^{II} , $\alpha\text{-CH}_2$ protons exhibit triplet at δ 2.74–2.77 ppm (J 6–7 Hz) and other methylene protons exhibit a broad peak at δ 1.27–1.30 ppm. Upfield shifting of α - and $\beta\text{-CH}_2$ protons in these complexes as compared to KIM supports the coordination of nitrogen to metal atom in the macrocyclic complexes.

Methyl and methylene protons of the ketone residue of macrocyclic complexes exhibit very weak signals. In the Mg^{II} complex (3) of macrocycle derived from 2,3-pentanedione CH_3^c protons appear as a triplet at δ 0.85 ppm due to the long range coupling with $\alpha\text{-CH}_2$ protons

of amine residue, similar to the homoallylic type coupling observed in the compounds having unsaturated linkage of the type $\text{H}_3\text{CC}=\text{NCH}_2$ ¹⁰.

The CH_3^a protons of the ketone moiety give rise to a triplet at δ 0.81 ppm, while the CH_2^b protons of the ethyl group appear as a multiplet at δ 2.29 ppm. In free 2,3-pentanedione ($\text{CH}_3^c\text{COCOCH}_2^b\text{CH}_3^a$) the CH_3^c protons give a singlet at δ 2.35 ppm, CH_3^a protons exhibit a triplet at δ 1.06 ppm, while CH_2^b protons give a quartet at δ 2.74 ppm. The high field shifting of CH_3^c protons of the methyl group and CH_2^b protons of ethyl group in the complexes confirms the coordination of nitrogen of macrocycle to the metal atom. However, the CH_3^a protons of ethyl group are very slightly shifted as these are away from the $\text{C}=\text{N}$ group and are not affected much by coordination.

In the complex of the macrocycle derived from 2,3-hexanedione the peaks of the protons of ketone residue are almost at the same positions as in the complex of macrocycle derived from 2,3-pentanedione.

In the NMR spectrum of Mg^{II} complex (4) of the macrocycle derived from 1-phenyl-1,2-propanedione and

diamine the CH₃^a protons give a singlet at δ 2.05 ppm. This is in good harmony with the Zn^{II} complexes of MePhTIM reported by Jackels *et al.*¹¹. The aromatic protons give very weak broad signals at δ 7.51 and 7.88 ppm.

Experimental

Materials : 2,3-Pentanedione (Fluka), 2,3-hexanedione (Aldrich), 1-phenyl-1,2-propanedione (Aldrich) and 1,7-diaminoheptane (Aldrich) were used as supplied. MgCl₂.6H₂O (B.D.H.), Ca(NO₃)₂.4H₂O (B.D.H.), SrCl₂.6H₂O (E. Merck) and BaCl₂.2H₂O (Glaxo) were of

A.R. grade. Methanol, ethanol and butanol were distilled before use.

Analytical methods and physical measurements : Magnesium, calcium and strontium were determined volumetrically using EDTA, barium gravimetrically as barium sulphate, nitrogen by Kjeldahl's method and chloride gravimetrically as AgCl. IR spectra were recorded on a Nicolet Magna-550 FTIR spectrophotometer as KBr pellets in the region 400–4000 cm⁻¹. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded in DMSO-*d*₆ on a Zeol FX 90Q FT NMR spectrometer using TMS as reference. Conductances were measured in DMSO using a Systronics Direct Reading Conductivity Meter-304.

Synthesis of Mg^{II} complexes of tetraazamacrocycles : To a butanolic solution of MgCl₂.6H₂O (2.6 mmol in ~25 ml), a butanolic solution of 2,3-pentanedione (5.2 mmol in 10 ml) was added. Then a butanolic solution of 1,7-diaminoheptane (5.2 mmol in 10 ml) was added to this under continuous stirring. The contents were stirred for ~6 h and the solid product obtained was filtered, washed with butanol and dried under reduced pressure. Similarly, the reactions of MgCl₂.6H₂O were carried out with 1,7-diaminoheptane and 2,3-hexanedione or 1-phenyl-1,2-propanedione to afford Mg^{II} complexes of 22-membered

Table 1. Analyses and characteristics of M^{II} complexes of tetraazamacrocycles

Complex	Colour and temp. of decomp. (°C)	Yield (%)	Analyses (%) : Found/(Calcd.)			Molar cond. (Ω ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹)
			M	N	Cl	
[(Me ₂ Et ₂ [22]tetraeneN ₄)MgCl ₂]	Yellow (195)	28	4.87 (5.02)	11.37 (11.57)	14.69 (14.65)	50
[(Me ₂ Pr ₂ [22]tetraeneN ₄)MgCl ₂]	Light brown (220)	20	4.66 (4.74)	10.86 (10.94)	13.83 (13.85)	76
[(Me ₂ Ph ₂ [22]tetraeneN ₄)MgCl ₂]	Light brown (205)	10	4.06 (4.19)	9.61 (9.66)	12.08 (12.22)	102
[(Me ₂ Et ₂ [22]tetraeneN ₄)Ca(NCS) ₂]	Light yellow (230)	19	7.25 (7.35)	10.25 (10.28)	–	73
[(Me ₂ Pr ₂ [22]tetraeneN ₄)Ca(NCS) ₂]	White (240)	29	6.79 (6.99)	9.77 (9.77)	–	158
[(Me ₂ Ph ₂ [22]tetraeneN ₄)Ca(NCS) ₂]	Olive green (195)	31	6.22 (6.25)	8.71 (8.74)	–	167
[(Me ₂ Et ₂ [22]tetraeneN ₄)Sr(NCS) ₂]	Brown (180)	71	14.78 (14.79)	9.42 (9.45)	–	23
[(Me ₂ Pr ₂ [22]tetraeneN ₄)Sr(NCS) ₂]	Brownish yellow (190)	23	14.11 (14.12)	9.02 (9.02)	–	26
[(Me ₂ Et ₂ [22]tetraeneN ₄)Ba(NCS) ₂]	Light brown (195)	13	21.35 (21.38)	8.70 (8.72)	–	17
[(Me ₂ Pr ₂ [22]tetraeneN ₄)Ba(NCS) ₂]	Brown (200)	15	20.47 (20.49)	8.30 (8.35)	–	15

Table 2. ¹H NMR chemical shifts (δ, ppm) of tetraazamacrocyclic complexes

Complex	Amine residue		Ketone residue		Aromatic protons
	α-CH ₂	β-CH ₂	CH ₃ ^{a,c}	CH ₂ ^b	
[(Me ₂ Et ₂ [22]tetraeneN ₄)MgCl ₂]	2.74t	1.27b	0.81t, 0.85t	2.29m	–
[(Me ₂ Pr ₂ [22]tetraeneN ₄)MgCl ₂]	2.74t	1.30b	0.84t	2.38m	–
[(Me ₂ Ph ₂ [22]tetraeneN ₄)MgCl ₂]	2.77t	1.27b	2.05s	–	7.51b, 7.88b

s = singlet, t = triplet, m = multiplet, b = broad.

tetraazamacrocycles.

Synthesis of Ca^{II} complexes of tetraazamacrocycles : To the butanolic solution of Ca(NO₃)₂·4H₂O (1.1 mmol in ~20 ml), a butanolic solution of 2,3-pentanedione (2.2 mmol in 10 ml) was added. To this, butanolic solution of 1,7-diaminoheptane (2.2 mmol) was added with continuous stirring. As no solid appeared a butanolic solution of potassium thiocyanate (2.2 mmol) was added. The contents were stirred for ~8 h and the temperature was maintained at 70 °C throughout the course of the reaction. The solid product obtained was filtered, washed with butanol and dried under reduced pressure. Similarly, the reactions of Ca(NO₃)₂·4H₂O were carried out with 1,7-diaminoheptane and 2,3-hexanedione or 1-phenyl-1,2-propanedione to afford corresponding Ca^{II} complexes of 22-membered tetraazamacrocycles.

Synthesis of Sr^{II} complexes of tetraazamacrocycles : To the methanolic solution of SrCl₂·6H₂O (1.9 mmol in ~20 ml), a methanolic solution of 2,3-pentanedione (3.8 mmol in 10 ml) was added. Then 1,7-diaminoheptane (3.8 mmol) was added drop by drop with continuous stirring. As no solid appeared, a methanolic solution of potassium thiocyanate (3.8 mmol) was added with constant stirring. Stirring was continued for ~10 h. The solid product obtained was filtered, washed with methanol and dried under reduced pressure. Similarly, the reaction of SrCl₂·6H₂O was carried out with 1,7-diaminoheptane and 2,3-hexanedione and Sr^{II} complex of corresponding 22-membered tetraazamacrocyclic was isolated.

Synthesis of Ba^{II} complexes of tetraazamacrocycles : BaCl₂·2H₂O (2.0 mmol) was dissolved in ethanol water (1 : 1) and an ethanolic solution of 2,3-pentanedione (4.0 mmol) was added. To this, 1,7-diaminoheptane (4.0 mmol in 10 ml ethanol) was added drop by drop with continuous stirring. Stirring was continued for ~10 h. The solid product

obtained was filtered, washed with ethanol and dried under reduced pressure. Similarly, the reaction of BaCl₂·2H₂O with 1,7-diaminoheptane and 2,3-hexanedione was carried out to give the Ba^{II} complex of the corresponding 22-membered tetraazamacrocyclic.

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